

Use of online collaborative tools in information services: an intervention project in scholarly communication

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Abstract

Academic libraries are created to support the curriculum, teaching, learning and research of academic staff and students of higher education institutions. For that purpose, academic libraries can provide a wide variety of information services to support the educational context in which they operate. Thus, the library information services of higher education institutions need to promote and enhance their users' skills related to the scientific and academic communication of undergraduate and graduate students. In higher education, one of the most common problems of first-year students, and also of other ones, is the difficulty in knowing and applying the rules of writing and presentation

of scientific and academic papers that they must submit to be evaluated. Several studies show a significant lack of knowledge on the part of students about these subjects. Based on this background, as a final project of an Information and Communication Technologies course, from an undergraduate course in Information Science, a student team carried out a project work to create a training course on academic writing. A set of collaborative online tools were used, and a wide range of outputs to support the training course was conceived. This paper aims to present the methodology followed in carrying out this project work, and the outcomes created, using a set of collaborative online tools, (Trello, Asana, Sway, Powtoon and Canva) to plan, manage, disseminate and implement this training course on academic writing, for undergraduate students of a Faculty of Arts and Humanities. This work shows that free online collaborative tools offer new possibilities for information services to create activities and materials with little investment.

Keywords: collaborative tools, project management, information units, academic library

Introduction

Information units, such as libraries and archives, develop initiatives for a varied audience. These activities need to be planned, managed, presented, and disseminated to the people they are intended for. To attend these needs, numerous free and easy-to-use online collaborative tools exist. These tools are gaining prominence as it is possible to use them online, performing practically the same functions as tools that a few years ago would have had to be stored on computers, with a requirement for payment in order to download them.

Thus, in an Information and Communication Technologies course, within an Information Science undergraduate degree at the University of Coimbra (Portugal), students were requested to conceive a project related to information services, and create the needed materials using an array of free online collaborative tools. One of the student teams decided to approach the topic of academic writing. They managed all the project steps and created dissemination materials using five free online collaborative tools.

This paper first presents a theoretical background focusing on the need for academic libraries to promote new services for their users, including topics related to academic writing. Then objectives and methodology are presented. The results of the project are shown, explaining the features of the online collaborative tools used, and presenting all the materials created. Some conclusions are drawn from the experience provided by this project; they focus on using free online collaborative tools to help academic libraries to offer new services, including a course on academic writing.

Theoretical background

The Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL), a division of the American Library Association (ALA), states that academic libraries provide resources and services to support the learning, teaching, and research needs of students, faculty, and staff (ACRL, 2018).

According to González Guitián & Molina Piñeiro (2008), academic libraries are institutions that gather, organise and disseminate information for learning, teaching and research, and that foster the creation of new knowledge. But academic libraries can also be seen as centres that contribute to the development of culture and the transmission of local values to the community they serve. This generates a strong cultural and social impact. The main

aim of these university or academic libraries is to provide access to a book collection and other information resources. They also aim to offer training to students in order to ensure they can use the resources of the library collection, and also to help them achieve academic success.

Following World War II, the higher education sector grew rapidly, in terms of the number of institutions, students, and courses offered. This pattern, common to all Western countries, had a massive impact on university libraries, which had to change and grow (Dempsey & Malpas, 2017). A SCONUL report reinforces this idea, underlining the role of academic libraries in supporting higher education: “Academic libraries currently operate within and contribute to a rapidly changing environment. Being aware of what is changing and ensuring that libraries can continue to play a useful role in higher education (HE) is a profound ongoing challenge” (Pinfield, Cox, & Rutter, 2017, p. 4).

One of the main areas in which academic libraries can support and improve the higher education institution they belong to is scholarly communication (Klain-Gabbay & Shoham, 2016). In the past, university faculties usually had no general libraries; instead colleges or departments had their own libraries. Their main objective was to attend to academic staff and students with a particular profile, and well-delimited information needs. With the growth of the higher education sector, academic libraries have become a service with a large dimension, serving a larger, diversified public comprising students and academic staff. The main objective of these larger libraries is to satisfy the information needs of their public target, emphasising the needs of its users, which have become more demanding, due not only to the development of the information society, but also of information and communication technologies.

These developments in the information society, but also of information and communication technologies led to many changes in university libraries, and digital libraries inevitably developed, which quickly changed the way they process and disseminate information.

On the other hand, according to Mukherjee (2009), the growth of information technologies has greatly expanded scientific communication in recent years, which has become easy, rapid, and global. This idea is reinforced by Klain-Gabbay & Shoham (2016, p. 171) when they report that

“with these advances, the traditional means of scholarly communication - both formal (e.g., publication of articles in peer-reviewed journals) and informal (e.g., personal and conference meetings, telephone calls, mail, and other informal channels) - have been supplemented with newer means of communication such as the use of e-mail and electronic databases; the publication of new conferences, journals and publications by way of the Internet; and the participation of individual scholars and scholarly groups in professional virtual communities, where Internet-based chats are conducted, blogs are shared, comments and suggestions are raised (e.g., on onlinepublished research manuscripts), and forum discussions are held”.

Since there are more and more information resources and more access to digital formats, as well as more and better means of communication, an environment has been created conducive to the emergence of plagiarism, derived, above all, from social changes in libraries, which provide the means to obtain information on any medium. Hence, it is crucial to hold workshops and lectures, among other training actions aimed at students of higher education, so that they become aware of methods to perform citations and bibliographical references, and, therefore, to improve their academic writing. Sanches (2019) focused on the relationship between information literacy skills and academic

writing. In academia, when students know how to search, locate, select, synthesise and present information in an ethical and legal manner, they improve the scientific validity of their texts. With this assumption we can conclude that through information literacy it is possible to significantly improve the effectiveness of academic writing (Sanches, 2019).

Methodology and objectives

As explained earlier, this paper presents the results from a project-based learning approach carried out in an Information and Communication Technologies course, from an undergraduate degree in Information Science. Students were required to work in a team group to plan, conceive and manage a project suitable for an information service, using free online collaborative tools. The teaching methodology followed a project-based learning approach as defined by Krauss & Boss (2013). Project-based learning involves five main characteristics: a) addressing real-world concerns and achieving a high level of understanding, b) personalisation as students choose the topic they work with, c) fostering questioning on the part of students, which leads to enquiries that bring them face to face with complexity d) students learn together and with each other, and their learning is meaningful beyond academia, and e) students are personally influenced by what they learn and are more likely to remember their learning.

One of the student teams chose to work with scholarly communication and to create a course on academic writing to be implemented by the academic library in a Faculty of Arts and Humanities.

Thus, they worked with a proposal of an implementation project to apply in a real setting, that they conceived in a simulation context.

This paper aims to present the methodology followed in this project work and the outputs created, using a set of collaborative online tools, (Trello, Asana, Sway, Powtoon and Canva) with freemium features, to plan, manage, disseminate and implement this training course on academic writing, for undergraduate students of a Faculty of Arts and Humanities.

The methodology that guided the project involved team collaboration among students. They browsed user guides provided by the collaborative tools and explored the features of each tool, with a hands-on approach. A simulation environment was defined in order to have a context in which this intervention project for academic writing would be framed. Then the tools to manage the entire project and create the support materials for its dissemination were chosen, and are presented in this paper.

To manage every step of the project, Trello was used. Asana was selected to present the public schedule of the training course. In order to promote the project and explain its functionality, Sway was used. To create the necessary media material for the dissemination of all the activities included in the project, Powtoon and Canva were used. For the dissemination of the workshop sessions, only Canva was used. In the following text, a synthesis of the functionalities used in each tool and the resources used will be presented.

Results of the project

Collaborative tools are software or applications that are used for sharing information between two or more people, allowing multiple people to be working in the same activity without meeting in a common physical work

environment. Each tool had unique features and functionalities to meet audience needs. So it is important to know what we need to do in order to choose the appropriate tool, and also to know the features offered by each tool.

First, the team needed a tool to manage the project; Trello was chosen. Trello, as any other project management tool, enables scheduling and listing tasks, allowing the creation of lists and cards that contain more specific information to help users to know what to do and when. With Trello it is possible to describe tasks, create checklists, implement completion dates, attach several kinds of files and assign labels, among other aspects. Trello [Figure 1, Figure 2] was used not only to plan the steps of the project, but also to specify what should be done with the other collaborative tools used. So cards in Trello included references to Canva, Sway and Powtoon, used to disseminate the project, and to Asana, where the calendar of the lectures and workshops of the course on academic writing were registered.

Figure 1: Project planning: Trello cards list

Figure 2: Project planning: Trello checklist

Asana is a tool that consists of scheduling or enumerating tasks, enabling users to create checklists, thus helping to organise, track, and manage work. The team used Asana [Figure 3] to schedule all the related aspects with the lecture dates and workshops. So Asana was used as a calendar or a timeline to spread and share the activities with students interested in participating in this academic writing course. This was possible because it is possible to include members who can view the calendar without editing it.

Figure 3: Schedule of lectures and workshops for April available on Asana calendar

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Figure 4: Some parts of the newsletter on Sway

In order to elaborate a promotion video of the planned lectures, Powtoon was used [Figure 5]. It is used to create animated videos from scratch or through existing models, which can be 100% streamlined. Although it contains many materials that can be used for free, there are still many that need to be paid for in order to use them. The video was created from scratch using the elements provided by the tool.

Figure 5: Promotion video on Powtoon

Canva is a graphic design tool used to create graphic content related to social media, presentations, infographics, posters, videos and other visual content. It enables the preparation of individual or group work, allowing real-time collaboration and interconnected comments so that there is communication between all members of the team. You can plan, create, schedule and directly publish posts on social networks.

Canva was chosen to create the poster and posts for social media about the lectures and workshops, due to its intuitive, easy and practical character [Figure 6]. To disseminate the work developed in Canva, a fictitious account on a social network (Instagram) was created. The reason for choosing this social network was the fact that Instagram is the social network most used by young people, who are the target audience of the course on academic writing.

Figure 6: Instagram feed with materials created with Canva

One of the aspects relevant to the success of the lectures and workshops was the preparation of posters to be affixed on the walls in the corridors of the Faculty of Arts and Humanities, in order to make students aware of the academic writing course and enable their participation. For this purpose, two posters were prepared, one for the lectures and another for the workshops. The posters delivered information about subjects, dates and places.

As the course on academic writing was aimed at a young community linked to the digital age, an account on Instagram social network was used to spread the whole project. Posts about the lectures and workshops were created, retaining similar formatting and branding to their corresponding posters. The posters feature a light blue background, superimposed by a dark blue rectangle, where the information is contained. They also feature images related to the project and other graphic elements. To disseminate information about academic writing, a post was created to give the details of it, and to make higher education students aware of its relevance for them.

The post [Figure 7] comprised six pages: the first corresponded to the design of two templates and the remaining pages were created from scratch in Canva. All pages followed the same template and colour palette. Blue was the predominant colour, since it is the colour of the faculty logo and the academic writing logo.

Figure 7: Some posts of academic writing

The idea of creating a logo [Figure 8] came about to represent the project. Considering that the logo of the Faculty of Arts and Humanities is blue, we use it as the main colour in the logo. The information implemented in the logo refers to the theme of the project: “Academic Writing” and our faculty. It is also important to mention that the entire design of the work, regarding the level of colours used, is related to the colour of the logo.

Figure 8: Logo of the academic writing course

To organise the lectures and workshops for May, monthly agendas were created to inform students about the activities that would take place during this month [Figure 9].

Figure 9: Posts about the April agenda

By the end of the project, a vast array of materials were created allowing an optimal dissemination of the academic writing course. The aim of the project was not to conceive the specific content that an academic writing should include, but instead to use free collaborative tools to plan, manage and disseminate the course. This approach shows that with no financial investment, as free tools were used, and with a limited learning effort, librarians can take advantage of several tools to improve their work and provide a new image of library services.

Conclusion

With this work, we intend to identify and present a set of online tools, with free usage options, that enable managing, presenting, and disseminating activities developed in an information service. As was expected with a project learning approach, students improved their skills for real use in a professional context. Furthermore, they learned about some tools that may also help them in their academic path. For example, Canva end up being advantageous for the realisation of academic work, as it is possible to use it to prepare not only presentations, but also written work. Trello is also a good tool for students to organise their own work study. Sway, which allows the creation of presentations, newsletters or a micro website, is a tool that students can explore for the design of a small personal web page.

On the other hand, the choice of academic writing as a topic for the project was due to the lack of skills and/or adaptation to the university context presented by most students throughout their academic careers. Thus, one of the objectives of this work was to underline the need to improve the students' writing techniques, through the creation of lectures and workshops.

The use of online collaborative tools allowed the management of all the steps of the project work and the creation of a large number of graphic materials. It was also an opportunity to work with tools that can help information services to develop creative activities and materials with little investment. Thus, students understood that collaborative tools offer new possibilities for information services to perform their functions. The students in the team gained greater awareness of the importance to information services of organising innovative activities, and helping users to solve concrete problems. In this case, academic libraries can improve students' skills in academic writing.

The final aspect is that, in a global approach, this project highlights the main advantages of all collaborative online platforms, making it possible to organise processes with a focus on productivity distribution across multiple team collaborators, and to establish priority levels as well as delivery times. Trello and Asana are good examples of that.

The students also showed a critical approach to online collaborative tools. As main drawbacks of each platform, it is noteworthy that some of the content is only accessible after payment. The slow response of one site, Powtoon, because it takes a while to stream, is also a drawback. However, despite the setbacks found on each platform, it was possible to create visually appealing and inviting final products, in a relatively easy and pragmatic way.

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